

The Role of Renewable Energies for Sustainable Energy Governance and Environmental Policies for the Mitigation of Climate Change in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT:

In response to the escalating global challenges posed by climate change, this research investigates the role of renewable energies in shaping sustainable energy governance and environmental policies for climate change mitigation in Nigeria. The study underscores the pivotal relationship between renewable energies and governance structures, emphasizing the need for innovative policy approaches. In Nigeria, a country grappling with a surge in energy demand, particularly in densely populated urban areas, this research delves into the current state of renewable energy adoption, technological aspects, and the policy and regulatory frameworks governing its integration. The study scrutinizes the technological aspects of solar, wind, hydropower, and biomass energy in Nigeria, exploring advancements in solar photovoltaic, hydropower, bioenergy, and geothermal technologies. Additionally, it dissects the nation's policy landscape, assessing key initiatives such as the National Energy Policy, the National Policy and Guidelines on Renewable Electricity, and Feed-in Tariffs. Furthermore, the research examines the alignment of environmental policies with renewable energy goals, highlighting the importance of targets, incentives, and regulatory frameworks. It also scrutinizes incentives for sustainable practices in Nigeria, including investment tax credits, the Renewable Energy Development Fund, and concessional import duty rates for renewable equipment. The study assesses the impact of renewable energy initiatives in Nigeria, gauging investment trends, ongoing projects, and the effectiveness of policy frameworks. It also delves into the economic, social, and environmental co-benefits of renewable energy projects, emphasizing their role in job creation, investment attraction, and reduction in energy costs. Finally, the research evaluates the effectiveness of renewable energy initiatives in reducing the nation's carbon footprint and fostering environmental sustainability. It highlights progress in achieving climate change mitigation goals through increased renewable energy capacity, policy frameworks, and off-grid electrification initiatives.

Keywords: renewable energies, sustainable energy governance, environmental policies, mitigation of climate change, Nigeria.

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INTRODUCTION

In the face of the extraordinary worldwide difficulties presented by climate change, it is crucial to prioritise the shift towards sustainable energy systems. Renewable energies, including solar, wind, hydro, and geothermal power, are seen as promising answers in the pursuit of sustainable energy [1]. These sources, unlike traditional fossil fuels, have the potential for clean and limitless electricity. The use of renewable energy is not just an environmental decision but also a strategic transformation that has significant consequences for sustainable development [2]. The core of this transformation is the notion of sustainable energy governance, which encompasses the integration of social, economic, and environmental factors into energy decision-making processes. Renewable energies act as catalysts for restructuring governance systems, requiring novel policy approaches that go beyond established energy paradigms. Governments globally are obligated to modify and restructure their energy policy to fit the decentralised and varied characteristics of renewable energy sources [3]. Environmental policies are crucial in facilitating this shift by providing the necessary regulations to effectively incorporate renewable energies into a country's energy systems. These policies establish goals for the use of renewable energy and also provide incentives for research and development, investment, and the establishment of a favorable environment for the growth of clean energy technology [1]. The progressive elimination of fossil fuel subsidies and the rise of carbon pricing systems amply demonstrate the interdependent relationship between renewable energy and environmental policy.

Nigeria's strategic significance in the context of climate change cannot be underestimated as the globe grapples with its implications. Energy is the cornerstone of Nigeria's economic growth and development [4]. The nation's foreign diplomacy heavily relies on it since it acts as a marketable commodity that generates national wealth. This cash is then used to finance government development projects. Additionally, it functions as a crucial factor in the generation of commodities and services in many areas of the nation's industry, transport, agriculture, health, and education [4]. Furthermore, it acts as a tool for politics, security, and diplomacy. The country has the challenging responsibility of not only guaranteeing dependable and easily obtainable energy for its people but also managing the intricacies of sustainable energy governance to comply with global environmental objectives. To achieve this delicate equilibrium, one must possess a sophisticated comprehension of the interconnections and conflicts between the integration of renewable energy, governance frameworks, and environmental regulations [5]. Nigeria, being the most densely populated nation in Africa, is now seeing a significant increase in the need for energy. The rise may be linked to the convergence of variables such as fast population growth, rapid industrialization, and rapid urban development. As metropolitan areas grow and industries increase, the pressure on the current energy infrastructure becomes increasingly noticeable.

The previous dependence on fossil fuels, which was formerly a catalyst for economic development, now poses a dual difficulty. Throughout its history, Nigeria has mostly relied on fossil resources, particularly oil and gas. Nigeria's federal income is mostly derived from energy, namely oil and gas, which account for more than 70% [6]. Revenues play a crucial role in supporting national developmental projects and ensuring security. Over the last five years, energy, particularly crude oil, has made up over 25% of Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product (GDP), making it the largest contributor after agricultural output [7]. When considering the utilisation of renewable energy, which makes up around 90% of the energy used by rural communities, it is anticipated that the contribution of energy to GDP will be greater. Oil and gas not only contribute considerably to carbon emissions, worsening the global climate problem, but they also make Nigeria susceptible to the unpredictable changes in the worldwide oil market [5]. In order to offset these issues, Nigeria is obligated to reassess and broaden its energy portfolio. The need for resilience against the detrimental effects of climate change

is emphasised by the escalating occurrence of severe weather events, escalating sea levels, and disturbances to agricultural patterns. The need to guarantee long-term sustainability extends beyond current economic factors and includes a wider range of environmental, social, and economic components. Nigeria's energy portfolio diversification represents a significant change in approach, aiming to use a wider range of energy sources. Renewable energy sources, including solar, wind, hydro, and biomass, are becoming crucial participants in this revolutionary process [8]. In addition to offering cleaner options that reduce the environmental impact, they also provide a means to achieve energy independence and security. This change is not only a reaction to worldwide demands for sustainability but rather a calculated decision to protect Nigeria's energy sector from unforeseen disruptions and lay the foundation for a strong and sustainable future. Renewable energy sources are now seen as a notable source of hope and potential. Solar, wind, hydro, and biomass, among other options, are feasible and environmentally friendly alternatives to traditional energy sources. Nigeria has the chance to use its plentiful renewable resources, leading to a more robust and ecologically conscious energy future [9]. An important advantage of integrating renewable energies into Nigeria's energy system is the improvement of energy security. To enhance energy security, the country may strengthen its position by diversifying its energy sources and decreasing its reliance on limited fossil fuels [6]. Diversifying energy sources reduces the susceptibility that comes with depending largely on traditional sources, thereby guaranteeing a more robust and resistant energy system. By tapping into its renewable resources, Nigeria not only satisfies its energy requirements in an environmentally friendly manner but also establishes itself as a centre for eco-friendly technology, enticing both local and international investors. Consequently, this helps in the establishment of a strong and varied economy.

The successful integration of renewable energies into mainstream energy systems is crucial for effectively addressing the urgent global issue of climate change [10]. The mitigation of greenhouse gas emissions, which is a direct outcome of transitioning to clean energy sources, plays a crucial role in worldwide endeavours to restrict the increase in global temperatures. Renewable energies not only serve as a substitute for energy sources that produce high levels of carbon but also provide the ability to withstand and recover from the effects of climate change. The deployment of renewable energy has the potential to reduce socioeconomic inequalities by encouraging inclusive growth. Local communities may gain autonomy and access to clean and cost-effective energy via the implementation of decentralised renewable energy systems. Consequently, this leads to improved living conditions, education, and healthcare, promoting a fairer allocation of the advantages of energy availability [8]. As marginalised communities get renewable energy, it serves as a catalyst for social advancement, dismantling obstacles to development. Furthermore, renewable energy offers a wide range of advantages that go beyond just reducing emissions. Distributed renewable energy sources enable local communities to take control of energy production, enhance energy security, and reduce the risks associated with centralised energy networks [9]. The democratisation of energy is in accordance with the ideals of sustainable development, since it fosters inclusion and ensures fair access to resources.

RENEWABLE ENERGY ADOPTION IN NIGERIA

Current State of Renewable Energy Adoption in Nigeria

Solar Energy: Nigeria is situated in a region with abundant sunlight, making it very suitable for harnessing solar energy. The mean annual average of total solar radiation ranges from around 3.5 kWhm⁻² day⁻¹ at coastal latitudes to around 7 kWhm⁻² day⁻¹ in the semi-arid regions of the far north. The country's average solar radiation level is around 19.8 MJm² day⁻¹. The projected average duration of sunlight is 6 hours per day [11]. The distribution of solar radiation is quite uniform. In January, the minimum average solar radiation in Katsina is around 3.55 kWhm⁻² day⁻¹, while in August, the lowest average in Calabar is about 3.4 kWhm⁻² day⁻¹. On the other hand, the highest average solar radiation in Nguru is 8.0 kWhm⁻² day⁻¹, occurring in May. Nigeria has made notable progress in the implementation of on-grid solar plants, particularly in metropolitan regions. These initiatives include the incorporation of solar energy into the national power system to complement

traditional energy sources. Rural and distant locations with limited access to the national grid have shown increasing interest in off-grid solar alternatives, such as solar household systems and mini-grids. Due to the country's substantial solar energy capacity, players in the energy sector are actively considering the implementation of solar energy projects. The 2022 edition of Tracking SDG 7: The Energy Progress Report reveals that among the population of over 200 million in Nigeria, a staggering 92 million individuals do not have access to power.

To narrow the access gap throughout the years, the federal government has cooperated with development agencies and other international organisations to examine the adoption of solar energy projects in the country [12]. An instance of this is when the Nigerian government initiated the Nigeria Electrification Project (NEP) in 2019. The project, which received funding from the World Bank (\$350 million), the Africa Growing Together Fund (\$50 million), and the African Development Bank (\$150 million), sought to increase electricity using solar power. Up to this point, the initiative has effectively linked 3.8 million individuals from Nigeria. Additionally, the occurrence of the Corona Virus (COVID-19) pandemic has necessitated an increased need for the implementation of renewable energy projects throughout the nation. The federal government implemented the Solar Power Naija (SPN) project as a component of its COVID-19 recovery plan to investigate the use of solar energy alternatives. The SPN programme has a value of \$619 million and its objective is to implement solar home systems for a total of 5 million families across the nation. In addition, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) implemented the solar intervention fund with the aim of promoting the growth of off-grid solution providers. The fund, designed to mitigate the impact of the epidemic, offers developers the chance to get loans of up to \$500 million. Recent efforts have led to a gradual and consistent rise in the implementation of solar energy projects in Nigeria [13]. However, the implementation of complementary structures must be a complement to the expansion of these energy initiatives. The Renewable Energy Master Plan (REMP) 2005 outlines Nigeria's objectives for renewable energy and seeks to identify the elements that influence the attainment of these objectives. Additionally, the National Renewable Energy Efficiency Policy of 2013 exists. The Federal Ministry of Power (FMOPT) formulated this strategy to enhance energy efficiency and address obstacles that hinder the implementation of renewable energy throughout the nation [12]. Nevertheless, several obstacles persist in the endeavour to implement solar energy initiatives in Nigeria, with access to financial resources being a prominent issue. Development agencies and the government establish financial initiatives, such as international and local grants and partnerships, to facilitate the procurement of finances for developers. Additionally, the federal government might provide help to scale solar projects in the nation by decreasing the manufacturing costs for developers.

Figure 1. Solar Radiation Map of Nigeria
Source: J.O. Ojosu, 1990 [29]

Wind Energy: Nigeria has shown enthusiasm for wind energy as a promising renewable resource. The wind has average speeds of about 2.0 m/s along the coast and 4.0 m/s in the far northern region of the country due to the uneven heating of the earth's surface by the sun and resulting pressure

differences. With an air density of 1.1 kg/m^3 , the wind energy intensity, perpendicular to the wind direction, varies from 4.4 W/m^2 in coastal regions to 35.2 W/m^2 in the far northern region [14]. Wind energy conversion systems, such as wind turbines, wind generators, wind plants, wind machines, and wind dynamos, are mechanisms that transform the kinetic energy of flowing air into the rotational motion of a shaft, namely mechanical energy. The methods for using this energy have been experimented with in the northern regions of the nation, mostly for extracting water from open wells in several secondary schools located in the former Sokoto and Kano States, as well as in Katsina, Bauchi, and Plateau States. A wind power conversion system with a capacity of 5 kW has been erected in Sayyan Gidan Gada, located in Sokoto State, with the purpose of electrifying the hamlet. Additional areas where wind energy conversion technologies might be used in Nigeria include generating "green electricity" for rural communities and integrating it into the national grid system. According to reports, a minimum average yearly wind speed of 5 m/s at a height of 10m above ground level is considered suitable for harnessing wind energy at current costs [14].

Figure 2. Isovents of Average Wind Speeds in m/s Based on 40 Year's Measurements (1968–2007) at 10m Height, Obtained from Nigeria Meteorological Department, Oshodi, Lagos State, Nigeria
Source: O. Ajayi, 2010 [30]

Hydropower: The Rivers Niger and Benue, together with their tributaries, provide significant opportunities for large-scale hydroelectric power generation in Nigeria. The Kainji, Jebba, and Shiroro dams are the three major hydroelectric projects in Nigeria, together providing a total capacity of 1930 MW [15]. Hydropower is a significant renewable energy source, accounting for around 30% of the overall capacity of the electricity system. However, the Renewable Energy Master Plan indicates that only around 14% of the nation's hydroelectric potential is now being used. Nigeria has abundant water resources. The coastal areas of the Niger Delta see an average annual rainfall of over 3400mm, while the northern parts receive a much lower amount of around 500mm. The average annual precipitation in the Jos Plateau area is around 1400mm, although in the eastern range it is over 2000mm [15]. The southern region of the country has a prolonged period of rainfall lasting around eight months each year, while the northern region sees a comparatively shorter amount of rainfall, lasting around three months annually [16]. The southern, plateau, and south-eastern regions are well-suited for hydropower development because of factors such as the amount and length of rainfall as well as the terrain. The projected capacity of the large-scale hydroelectric potential is 10,000, which corresponds to a total energy generation of 36,000 gigawatt-hours (GWh). The primary focus of the REMP is the advancement of small hydropower (SHP) projects. The data collected from 12 states indicates that there is a potential for 734 megawatts of small hydropower (SHP) from 277 locations. Furthermore, it suggests that the whole country may potentially generate about 2500

megawatts. Small hydropower plants (SHPs) have the potential to provide energy to isolated locations that are not connected to the main power grid. The SHP projects in Plateau, Sokoto, and Kano states have a combined installed capacity of 30 MW. Insufficient data gathering is a challenge to hydropower production in accurately determining the available potential [2]. Furthermore, the extended duration of project implementation is attributed to bureaucratic processes and the absence of technical norms for hydroelectric equipment. Water rights disputes arise in some instances when water is redirected.

Biomass/Bioenergy: Biomass encompasses all forms of living entities, such as plants, algae, microorganisms, and animals [17]. These substances consist of carbon, oxygen, nitrogen, and sulphur and contain substantial quantities of available energy in the form of chemical bonds. Upon the molecular disintegration, the energy may be liberated, resulting in the production of heat, which can then be transformed into mechanical energy or electrical power. Biomass may be converted into a liquid state and used as a feedstock for transportation fuel. Both food and non-food biomass may be used to generate biofuels, which can exist as solid, gaseous, or liquid substances. The term "solid biofuel" refers to the combustion of wood for both household and industrial purposes [18]. Microbes create biogas, which consists of methane, carbon dioxide, carbon monoxide, and hydrogen. Wood gas, derived from the chemical cracking of wood, is an alternative kind of solid biofuel. Due to the need for large and heavy tanks, gasoline is not considered an ideal fuel for transportation purposes. The primary use of this is for household purposes [19]. Liquid fuels are appealing because of their elevated energy densities and their ability to be stored in containers that are lightweight. The worldwide production and use of biofuels are anticipated to address several environmental issues, such as sustainability, climate change, and biodegradability. Nigeria has biomass resources such as wood, fodder grasses, bushes, and animal dung. Animal waste is another bioenergy source that is accessible in Nigeria. Nigeria is predicted to create around 227,500 metric tonnes of fresh animal waste per day. Given that 1 kilogramme of fresh animal waste yields around 0.03 m³ of biogas, Nigeria has the potential to generate over 6.8 million m³ of biogas every day only from the animal waste it produces. More than 80% of the Nigerian population relies on fuel wood for cooking and heating, but the present energy strategy of Nigeria has reduced the importance of using fuel wood for energy purposes [20]. The bioenergy resources in Nigeria have significant potential for generating bioelectric power, which might play a crucial role in addressing the country's electricity issue. The concept of bioenergy may face resistance in Nigeria, particularly when it involves food crops. One noteworthy aspect of the biofuel idea that might provide immediate advantages to Nigeria is the manufacturing of biogas waste. This method does not need irrigation or land utilisation and has the ability to improve environmental cleanliness [18]. Implementing biogas generation from waste will lead to a reduction in the use of firewood as an energy source in Nigeria. On a global scale, the production of biofuels is influenced by several variables, such as the utilisation and accessibility of feedstock, as well as inefficient production methods. The exorbitant expense of enzymes necessary for the digestion of feedstock on a large scale significantly impacts the cost of manufacturing in the biofuel business. Nevertheless, Nigeria has the necessary resources for biofuel and biogas production, although it lacks the technical expertise and infrastructure required for widespread bioenergy production.

Technological Aspects of Renewable Energy in Nigeria

Nigeria has been exploring various technological aspects of renewable energy to diversify its energy mix and address power challenges. Here are some technological aspects related to renewable energy in Nigeria:

Solar Photovoltaic (PV) Technology: Solar photovoltaic (PV) technology is an environmentally sustainable energy source that harnesses the power of sunshine to generate electricity. The global importance of this technology is increasing owing to its ability to mitigate carbon emissions and generate renewable energy [17]. Nigeria, as a developing nation, acknowledges the significance of embracing cutting-edge technology in solar photovoltaics. Solar photovoltaic (PV) technology uses solar panels to convert sunlight into direct current (DC) power. Afterwards, this energy is converted into alternating current (AC) electricity, which may then be used to provide power to homes, businesses, and the electrical grid. The development of new technology in solar photovoltaics, such as upgraded materials and enhanced efficiency, allows for more power production and lower costs.

Solar PV is an appealing choice for achieving energy sustainability and improving electricity access, especially in developing nations. Nigeria has acknowledged the capacity of solar photovoltaic (PV) technology to effectively tackle its energy-related difficulties. The country is now facing a growing need for power, and solar photovoltaic (PV) technology offers a feasible alternative to fulfill this need while decreasing dependence on fossil fuels. The government has enacted many measures to encourage the deployment of solar photovoltaic (PV) systems, such as providing financial incentives and establishing legislative frameworks [16]. Nigeria's attainment of its energy objectives and its contribution to global endeavors in addressing climate change heavily rely on the integration of cutting-edge technology in solar photovoltaic. Nigeria may achieve diversification of its energy mix, enhanced energy availability, and reduced greenhouse gas emissions by adopting solar PV technology. Solar photovoltaic (PV) technology has great potential for Nigeria's future, offering chances for sustainable development and economic expansion. Solar photovoltaic (PV) technology harnesses the energy from sunshine and transforms it into electrical power, providing a viable and environmentally friendly energy alternative. With an average of 6 to 7 hours of sunlight each day, Nigeria has abundant solar resources. Solar photovoltaic (PV) systems may be installed in both grid-connected and standalone configurations, therefore increasing the availability of power in distant regions. By investing in solar PV, Nigeria may effectively decrease greenhouse gas emissions and uphold its obligations to mitigate climate change [13]. In essence, solar photovoltaic (PV) technology has the potential to provide employment opportunities at the local level and foster economic growth. In general, Nigeria's present energy situation heavily depends on fossil fuels and encounters several obstacles, such as power interruptions, insufficient infrastructure, and restricted electricity availability in rural regions. Nevertheless, the nation is seeing a growing need for energy and an urgent desire for viable and environmentally friendly alternatives. The emergence of solar PV technology offers a practical solution by efficiently using ample solar resources to generate energy, whether connected to the main power grid or operating independently. Implementing solar photovoltaic (PV) systems not only mitigates the release of greenhouse gases but also enhances energy resilience and promotes economic development. Nigeria should unequivocally embrace the use of solar photovoltaic (PV) technology as an essential measure towards achieving a more environmentally friendly and enduring energy future.

Figure 3. Solar PV Installations in Nigeria

Source: Ecofriendly, Solar Power Bring Light to Dark Nigerian Village

Wind Energy Technology: Nigeria has discovered places with substantial wind potential; however, wind energy projects are still in their nascent phases. Wind farms use the energy from the wind to produce electrical power. Feasibility studies and exploration activities have been carried out to assess the suitability of certain locations for wind farm development [19]. Contrary to its usual meaning, "offshore" in the maritime industry and wind farm sector refers to places close to the shore, such as oceans, lakes, and sheltered coastal areas. Therefore, "offshore wind" refers to wind

resources found in these locations. In contrast, onshore wind refers to wind resources located on land. Offshore wind power, also known as offshore wind energy, refers to the use of turbines placed in offshore locations, often on the Continental Shelf, to harness wind energy for the purpose of generating electricity [14]. Offshore wind power production is greater due to the increased wind speed available at offshore sites in comparison to onshore locations. Offshore wind turbines provide distinct benefits over onshore wind turbines, including: (a) the ability to generate energy at a rate of around 3-5 MW per hour under high wind conditions; (b) consistency in wind speed; and (c) enhanced durability in comparison to onshore wind turbines [15]. The lifespan of this turbine is 25–30 years and it produces about 50% more energy than a turbine located on land. The primary impediments to future offshore wind farm projects are the financial expenses involved and the level of approval from the general public. Based on research findings and wind data collected from Nigerian meteorological stations, it has been determined that wind speeds are generally low in the southern region of Nigeria, with the exception of offshore areas spanning from Lagos to Akwa Ibom State. These areas have been identified as having significant potential for harnessing strong wind energy consistently throughout the year [14]. States such as Jos, Katsina, and Maiduguri have high wind speeds due to factors such as terrain and surface roughness. Subsequent investigation found that the northern region of Nigeria has the potential to harness wind speeds of around 8.07 m/s. Based on a recent analysis by NIMET, which analysed 40 years (1968– 2007) of wind data from 44 stations throughout Nigeria, it was found that the northern region of Nigeria has consistently high onshore wind speeds. Some of the challenges hindering the development of wind energy technology in Nigeria include insufficient research and technology in the field of wind energy, a lack of government support for the idea of wind energy technology, and difficulties with land ownership and acquisition in Nigeria, among others. Therefore, it is crucial for all levels of government to collaborate in addressing these issues. This includes raising awareness among local communities about the benefits of wind energy and creating a combination of the stated factors that would greatly contribute to the advancement of wind power production technology in Nigeria.

Hydroelectric technology: Nigeria now has operational hydropower facilities, including the Kainji and Jebba hydroelectric power units. These plants use the kinetic energy of moving water to produce electrical power. The continuous improvement of these plants via modernization and optimisation is a persistent endeavour [17]. Hydropower now produces a greater amount of energy compared to all other renewable technologies combined and is projected to continue being the primary source of renewable electricity production worldwide until the 2030s. Afterwards, it will persist in playing a crucial function in reducing carbon emissions from the power system and enhancing system adaptability.

Figure 4. Pumped Hydroelectric Energy

Source: Hydroelectric Energy, Bath County Storage Station, 2013

Bioenergy Technology: Investigations into bioenergy initiatives, such as the generation of biogas, have been conducted. Organic waste may be converted into biogas, which has many applications such as cooking, heating, and energy production. Biomass energy, which encompasses the use of agricultural leftovers for the purpose of generating electricity, is a subject that attracts attention. The process involves the transformation of organic substances into energy using several methods [16].

The methods used for the transformation of organic biomass resources into solid, liquid, and gaseous fuels have been in use for a considerable period in both developed and developing nations. Biogas is mostly used for domestic heating, cooking, and lighting, as well as for generating energy for agricultural and industrial operations. The exploration of biogas in Nigeria began in 1982 [5]. Subsequently, research efforts have been ongoing, albeit not with sufficient intensity to achieve the commercial viability of the technology within the nation. Currently, there are fewer than twenty pilot projects for biogas in the nation. These initiatives include biogas plants at Zaria jail in Kaduna, Ojokoro in Lagos, Mayflower School Ikene in Ogun State, and a biogas plant at Usman Danfodiyo University in Sokoto. The capacity of the digesters in these plants is between 10 and 20 m³ [21]. The UNDP brought the floating drum, plastic balloon, and tube kinds of biogas digesters to Yobe, Jigawa, and Kano States as part of the Africa 2000 low-technology biogas system. Since 2003, the Kwachiri village in Kano state has relied on the UNDP biogas project, which utilises cow dung, to meet their daily cooking requirements [4]. In a similar fashion, the UNDP implemented the use of biogas technology in selected market abattoirs located in the Northern States.

Geothermal Survey: Nigeria has significant geothermal resources, and much research has been performed to evaluate the viability of using geothermal energy. Geothermal power is the process of using the Earth's interior heat to generate energy. The user's text is "[15]". The geological composition and historical development in Nigeria have a significant impact on the investigation of geothermal energy within each geographical region. There are several products resulting from magmatic and volcanic processes in the Benue trough. The Biu plateau is home to more than 80 volcanoes, while the Jos plateau has large basaltic lava flows. Geothermal reservoirs are found worldwide and are generated in convectional systems, where hot water ascends from the depths of the earth and is trapped in reservoirs. Silification, a process that results in the precipitation of mineral components, is what gives these reservoirs their caprocks. Oil firms in Nigeria have extensively investigated sedimentary basins for hydrocarbons over many years, resulting in the accumulation of a significant amount of subsurface temperature data [18]. Analysis of data collected from oil wells and water wells in the Niger Delta region has shown that the geothermal gradient varies from 1.3 to 4.7°C per 100 metres. Water boreholes are also a valuable resource for obtaining information on subsurface temperatures. The temperature recorded during pumping experiments closely approximates the actual temperature of the aquifer formation. Nevertheless, it is common for these wells to have a shallow depth. Specifically, water wells dug in crystalline regions in Nigeria often do not exceed a depth of 30 metres [22]. Water boreholes in sedimentary environments often have greater depths, reaching up to 500 metres, and may serve as valuable sources of geothermal data. Nigeria has numerous warm and hot springs and seepages, primarily found in the sedimentary basin of the Benue Trough. These geological features are visible signs of geothermal energy in the subsurface, suggesting the presence of potential geothermal resources in this area.

Smart Grid Technology: Smart grid technologies are necessary for the incorporation of renewable energy sources into the national grid [20]. These technologies provide effective control of power distribution, demand-response systems, and live monitoring. The use of smart grid technology enables the efficient transmission of power from suppliers to consumers over a reliable and secure two-way digital communication system. This technology allows for the remote management of appliances in customers' homes, resulting in reduced energy consumption, improved dependability, and enhanced transparency, as seen in figure 2. It involves combining communication networks with the electrical power grid to create a highly efficient system that can continuously monitor its own condition, promptly notify the utility of any issues, and automatically implement corrective measures. This allows the grid to handle failures smoothly and prevent localised problems from escalating uncontrollably [21]. The traditional grid consists of a centralised power-producing system with electricity flowing in one direction at the distribution level and little interaction with the market. Smart Grid technology encompasses both centralised and distributed power production, mostly derived from renewable energy sources. The technology incorporates decentralised and operational resources like power production, electrical loads, energy storage, and electric cars into the energy markets and electric power systems [23]. The energy network intelligently connects producers and consumers to effectively provide power that is capable of providing a safe, economic, dependable, efficient, and sustainable system. One of two main objectives for the development of smart grid technology is typically to improve communication between energy providers and end users in the

electric power industry. The use of smart grid technology encompasses all aspects of the electrical system, including production, transmission, distribution, and consumption. Several writers, government organisations, and entities have provided several definitions of smart grids. A smart grid is an enhanced energy grid network that facilitates bidirectional information and power transfer between electricity providers and customers, thanks to the widespread integration of intelligent communication monitoring and management systems [24]. Exploring the Advantages and Consequences of Smart Grid Initiatives in the European Union and United States. The US Department of Energy (DOE) defines the smart grid as a system that incorporates digital technologies to improve the dependability, efficacy, and protection of the electric system. The International Energy Agency's Technology Roadmap The term "Smart Grid" denotes an energy network that employs digital and other advanced technologies to oversee and regulate the transmission of electricity from all power-producing sources in order to satisfy the fluctuating electricity requirements of end-users. It will arrange [14]. The grid operators, generators, end-users, and electrical market players need various skills and have specific demands to ensure the proper operation of all components of the system. This includes minimising environmental effects and costs while enhancing system dependability, resilience, and stability. In addition to its ability to balance supply and demand, the smart grid will also mitigate greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions [24] by decreasing reliance on fossil fuel power plants. This will be achieved through the integration of renewable energy sources, which will enhance the flexibility of the electric system and optimise usage efficiency. A smart grid uses digital technology to efficiently transmit power from suppliers to consumers. It does this via control automation, continuous monitoring, and optimisation of the distribution system. The primary goals of a smart grid are to save energy, decrease consumer expenses, and enhance reliability.

Figure 5. Incorporation of Renewable Energy into the Smart Grid

Source: A. Chaturvedi, 2020 [31].

Energy Storage Solutions: Energy storage solutions, particularly battery technologies, are crucial for ensuring a stable and reliable power supply from intermittent renewable sources. Advancements in battery technology contribute to grid stability and energy storage capacity [26]. Startups are offering battery and batteryless solutions for distributed energy storage systems (DESS), which help energy providers to generate and store energy in a decentralised way and overcome irregularities in production. One of the latest solutions in the discussion is solid-state batteries, which are lightweight and have a higher energy density.

Digital Platforms for Energy Management: Digital platforms and technologies play a role in managing and optimizing renewable energy systems [25]. These may include monitoring systems, predictive analytics, and digital platforms for energy management.

Policy Aspects and Regulatory Frameworks of Renewable Energy in Nigeria

A comprehensive and coherent energy policy is essential in guiding a country towards the efficient utilization of its energy resources. It must be stressed that while the existence of an energy policy is crucial, it does not guarantee the prudent responsibility management of a country's energy resources.

National Energy Policy, 2003, 2006, 2013

Nigeria has been working on developing policies and frameworks to promote renewable energy adoption and address energy challenges. The Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN) in 2003 approved the National Energy Policy (NEP) which was facilitated by the Energy Commission of Nigeria (ECN) to articulate the sustainable exploitation and utilization of all energy sources. The key elements of the NEP on the development and utilization of renewable energy and its technologies are as follows:

- To develop, promote and harness the renewable energy resources of Nigeria and incorporate all viable ones in the national energy mix;
- To promote decentralized energy supply, especially in rural areas, based on renewable energy resources;
- To deemphasize and discourage the use of wood as a fuel;
- To promote efficient methods in the use of biomass energy resources;
- To keep abreast of the international development in the renewable energy technologies and applications.

Renewable Energy Master Plan (REMP), 2005 and 2012

In 2005, the ECN also formulated the Renewable Energy Master Plan (REMP) as part of the strategy to reduce Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emission in Africa and address the challenges hindering the development of clean, reliable, secured and competitive energy supply. The REMP main objectives are given below:

- To develop and implement strategies that will achieve a clean reliable energy supply mechanism to develop the sector based on international best practices, to show case viability for private sector participation;
- To provide a comprehensive framework for developing renewable energy that will ensure: Expanding access to energy services to Nigerians; National agenda on emission reduction; Raising the standard of living, especially in the rural areas; Stimulating economic growth, employment and empowerment; Increasing the scope and quality of rural services, including schools, information, health services, entertainment, and water supply and reducing rural urban migration.

The REMP aims at a 10% renewable energy contribution to the national energy mix by 2020 through the adoption of a renewable portfolio standard (RPS). A RPS is a requirement for electric utilities to supply a specific amount of electricity to customers. This can be achieved through the purchase of renewable energy certificates from suppliers with a larger share of renewables in their energy mix. Other measures considered are the creation of innovative fiscal and market incentives to promote renewable energy industries, as well as preferential customs duty exemptions for imported renewable energy technology components. However, the lack of implementation of the master plan has meant that the 10% target of renewable energy mix in the energy supply cannot be achieved. The REMP is presently being subjected to a review, likely resulting in the setting of new targets. It will be essential that any future targets set for the attainment of a RE energy mix should be backed by legislation to ensure compliance, which is presently lacking.

National Policy and Guidelines on Renewable Electricity (NPGRE), 2006

The National Policy and Guidelines on Renewable Electricity (NPGRE) was produced in 2006 with the main aim to expand the market for renewable electricity by 5% of the total electricity generation by 2016. The strategy for achieving this target included: encouraging local manufacture and assembly of renewable energy components, provision of subsidies, and establishment of technical standards

for RE components and introduction of feed-in-tariffs. The strategy is yet to be fully adopted as the reforms in the energy sector are still ongoing and decisions on tariffs and subsidies for renewable energy and other incentives have not yet been taken.

Feed-in Tariffs (FiTs)

Feed-in Tariffs (FiTs) are policy mechanisms that set a fixed payment rate for electricity generated from renewable sources. Nigeria has explored the use of FiTs to incentivize private investment in renewable energy projects. The aim of FiTs is to provide a simple system to incentivize small domestic and business renewables. FiTs are the most effective policy to encourage the rapid and sustained development of RE. The scheme pays a tariff, which varies according to the technology and the size of the installation, for every kWh generated and the quality of resource. It also pays a small additional tariff for the lifetime of the scheme, which is linked to the retail price index. Further details about the functions of FiT systems and the evaluation criteria of different design options are described in . Renewable technologies have been on the rise worldwide through renewable energy FiTs. As of 2012, 65 countries have implemented some form of a FiT, driving 64% of global wind installations and 87% of the photovoltaic capacity that has been installed worldwide. While the majority of these installations have occurred in industrialized countries, particularly in Europe, USA, and China, the African continent, and Nigeria in particular, still have significant untapped RE potential. Some African countries like Kenya, Mauritius, Algeria, Tanzania, Rwanda, Egypt, Uganda and South Africa have introduced FiT. Ghana, Ethiopia, Botswana, Namibia and Nigeria are just developing or planning their FiTs. FiT policies provide a promising mechanism that can unlock RE development in Nigeria. It encourages investment in the generation of RE, from individual home owners and communities as well as big companies, by buying and paying made for all the electricity that is produced from renewable sources. FiTs are most successful when they are an integral part of a country's wider development strategy. Thus, high-level political support and strong buy-ins from civil society and the private sector are crucial factors for the successful development and implementation of the FiT. Therefore, Nigeria is encouraged to enact FiT laws to facilitate private sector investment in RE for electricity generation as well as to boost investment security. FiT payment can be funded through budgetary allocations; largely from savings arising from petroleum subsidy removal.

Electric Power Sector Reform Act (EPSRA), 2005

The enactment of the Electricity Power Sector Reform Act (EPSRA) of 2005 by the Federal Government marks the end of vertically integrated electric utility in Nigeria. The Act stipulates the unbundling and privatization of electricity sector thereby allowing IPPs to generate and sell to the national grid. The general aims of the reforms in Nigeria like deregulated electricity industries in other countries across the globe are to improve efficiency, to create a more competitive energy-producing industry, to attract new – outside – investors and also to divest the state of over-regulated, and often heavily indebted, electricity undertaking, providing welcome cash for the government that can be spent on social services. EPSRA established the National Electricity Regulatory Commission (NERC) to coordinate the activities of the deregulated electricity market. Rural Electricity Agency (REA) was also established with the statutory functions of promoting, supporting and providing electricity access to rural and semi-urban areas of the country. REA is responsible for administration of the Rural Electrification Fund (REF), which provides autonomous funding opportunity through the Renewable Electricity Trust Fund (RETF). Private individuals are also allowed to own and operate off-grid power generator with a capacity of less than 1 MW without acquiring electricity license from NERC and regardless of the fuel type. Recently, NERC signed two regulations – the Independent Electricity Distribution Network (IEDN) and Embedded Generation 2012. The regulation on embedded generation permits investors, communities, state and local governments to generate and distribute electricity for their exclusive consumption using facilities of existing electricity distribution companies or independent electricity distribution network operators, while the regulation on independent electricity distribution networks permits communities, local and state governments to invest in electricity distribution networks in areas without access to the grid or distribution network or areas poorly serviced. The regulations along with EPSRA will positively impact investments in RE power generation in Nigeria, especially in the remote communities where the cost of grid extension is

extremely high. The EPSRA provides a legal framework for the restructuring and development of Nigeria's electricity sector. Within this act, provisions support the participation of renewable energy projects in the national grid, promoting sustainable energy governance.

Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) Regulations:

EIAs are mandatory for large-scale energy projects in Nigeria. These regulations require developers to assess and mitigate potential environmental impacts before project approval. For renewable energy projects, EIAs contribute to sustainable governance by ensuring adherence to environmental standards.

The National Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Policy (NREEEP), 2014

The National Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Policy (NREEEP) outlines the global thrust of the policies and measures for the promotion of renewable energy and energy efficiency. The FMP developed the NREEEP in 2014 and is awaiting the approval of the Federal Executive Council.

ENVIRONMENTAL POLICIES AND RENEWABLE ENERGY ALIGNMENT

Overview of Environmental Policies and Regulations in Nigeria

Environmental policies and regulations are designed to manage and mitigate the impact of human activities on the environment, promote sustainable practices, and safeguard natural resources. The specifics of these policies and regulations vary across countries and regions, reflecting the unique environmental challenges each faces. The basis of environmental policy in Nigeria is contained in the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. Pursuant to section 20 of the Constitution, the State is empowered to protect and improve the environment and safeguard the water, air and land, forest and wildlife of Nigeria. In addition to this, section 2 of the Environmental Impact Assessment Act of 1992 (EIA Act) provides that the public or private sector of the economy shall not undertake or embark on or authorize projects or activities without prior consideration of the effect on the environment. In this regard, the Federal Government of Nigeria has promulgated various laws and Regulations to safeguard the Nigerian environment. These include:

1) Federal Environmental Protection Agency Act of 1988 (FEPA Act) repealed by the National Environmental Standards Regulation Agency (NESREA) Act 2007. The following Regulations were made pursuant to the FEPA Act:

- National Environmental Protection (Effluent Limitation) Regulations;
- National Environmental Protection (Pollution Abatement in Industries and Facilities Generating Wastes) Regulations; and
- National Environmental Protection (Management of Solid and Hazardous Wastes) Regulations.

2) Environmental Impact Assessment Act of 1992 (EIA Act).

3) Harmful Wastes (Special Criminal Provisions etc.) Act of 1988 (Harmful Wastes Act).

The National Environmental Standards Regulation Agency, (NESREA) (the agency) has the responsibility for the protection and development of the environment, biodiversity conservation and sustainable development of Nigeria's natural resources, environmental technology, including coordination and liaison with relevant stake holders within and outside Nigeria on matters of enforcement of environmental standards, regulations, rules, laws, policies and guidelines. Other regulatory agencies with oversight functions and responsibility over specific industries have also issued guidelines to regulate the impact of such industries on the environment such as the Environmental Guidelines and Standards for the Petroleum Industry in Nigeria (EGASPIN) 2002, published by the Department of Petroleum Resources (DPR). The NESREA Act allows each State and Local Government in the country to set up its own agency for the protection and improvement of the environment within the State. Each State is also empowered to make laws to protect the environment within its jurisdiction. All the States have environmental agencies and State laws; e.g. Lagos, Akwa Ibom, Abuja.

Alignment of Environmental Policies with Renewable Energy Goals

The alignment of environmental policies with renewable energy goals is crucial for achieving sustainable development and addressing environmental challenges, particularly in the context of mitigating climate change. Here are ways in which environmental policies are often aligned with renewable energy goals:

Renewable Energy Targets: Environmental policies often include specific targets for the adoption and integration of renewable energy sources in the overall energy mix. These goals may include a percentage of renewable energy in the total energy generation or specific capacity targets.

Incentives and Subsidies: Policies may offer financial incentives, subsidies, or tax credits to businesses and individuals investing in renewable energy projects. This encourages the adoption of renewable technologies by making them economically more attractive.

Regulatory Framework: Policies may address the integration of renewable energy into existing energy grids. This involves regulatory frameworks to facilitate the connection of renewable energy systems to the grid and ensure a smooth transition to cleaner energy sources.

Emission Reduction Targets: Environmental policies often include targets for reducing greenhouse gas emissions. Increased use of renewable energy contributes to these goals by displacing fossil fuel-based energy sources, which are major contributors to carbon emissions.

Renewable Portfolio Standards (RPS): Some regions implement Renewable Portfolio Standards, which mandate that a certain percentage of energy must come from renewable sources. These standards are backed by policy and help drive the adoption of renewable energy technologies.

Community Engagement: Policies may promote community engagement in renewable energy projects, ensuring that local communities benefit economically and socially from the development of renewable energy infrastructure.

Energy Efficiency Measures: Energy efficiency means an improvement in practices and products that reduce the energy necessary to provide services. Energy efficiency products essentially help to do more work with less energy. Energy efficiency is also defined as essentially using less energy to provide the same service. In this sense, energy efficiency can also be thought of as a supply of resource - often considered an important, cost-effective supply option. Investment into energy efficiency can provide additional economic value by preserving the resource base (especially combined with pollution prevention technologies) and mitigating environmental problems. Energy efficiency (EE) improvements have multiple advantages, such as the efficient exploitation of natural resources, the reduction in air pollution levels, and lower spending by the consumers on energy-related expenditure. Investments in EE result in long-term benefits, such as reduced energy consumption, local environmental enhancement, and overall economic development. Environmental policies often incorporate measures to improve energy efficiency in parallel with promoting renewable energy. Combining these efforts maximizes the overall impact on reducing environmental footprints.

Regulation of Fossil Fuels: Policies may include measures to phase out subsidies for fossil fuel industries, making renewable energy more competitive in the market and leveling the playing field for cleaner alternatives.

The alignment of environmental policies with renewable energy goals is an integrated and multidimensional process. Effective policies consider the entire energy ecosystem, economic implications, technological advancements, and societal impacts to create a framework that accelerates the transition to a sustainable and low-carbon energy future.

Incentives for Sustainable Practices in Nigeria

Renewable Energy Investment Tax Credits: The Nigerian government provides tax credits to businesses and investors involved in renewable energy projects. This financial incentive encourages private investment in sustainable energy solutions.

Renewable Energy Development Fund (REDF): The REDF, established by the Nigerian government, offers financial support and incentives to renewable energy projects. This fund aims to

bridge financial gaps and stimulate the growth of the renewable energy sector.

Concessionary Import Duty Rates for Renewable Equipment: To reduce the cost of renewable energy projects, Nigeria offers concessional import duty rates for renewable energy equipment. This incentive facilitates the importation of necessary technology and components for sustainable energy initiatives.

Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) in Renewable Energy: Nigeria encourages collaboration between the public and private sectors through PPPs. This approach facilitates the development of sustainable energy projects, leveraging private sector expertise and resources.

Green Bonds and Financing Mechanisms: Nigeria has explored the issuance of green bonds to fund environmentally sustainable projects, including renewable energy initiatives. These financial instruments attract investment from environmentally conscious investors.

Renewable Energy Certification and Standards: Certification programs and adherence to international standards for renewable energy projects can qualify developers for incentives. This promotes quality and reliability in sustainable energy practices.

Capacity Building and Research Grants: Incentives for capacity building and research in the renewable energy sector aim to enhance local expertise. Grants and support for educational programs contribute to a skilled workforce capable of driving sustainable energy projects.

Recognition and Awards for Sustainable Energy Practices: Recognition programs and awards highlight exemplary sustainable energy projects and practices. This not only celebrates achievements but also encourages the replication of successful models in the industry.

The alignment of regulatory frameworks and incentives in Nigeria reflects a commitment to fostering sustainable energy governance and addressing climate change challenges. These measures create an enabling environment for the widespread adoption of renewable energies, contributing to a more sustainable and resilient energy landscape in the country.

The Role of Government and Institutions

The government and various institutions contribute significantly to shaping and implementing policies that address environmental challenges and promote the adoption of renewable energies. Here are some key aspects of the role played by government and institutions in fostering the synergy between environmental policies and renewable energy in Nigeria:

Policy Formulation and Legislation: The Nigerian government, through relevant ministries and agencies, is responsible for formulating environmental policies and legislation. This includes setting targets for renewable energy adoption, emission reductions, and sustainable development practices. Government institutions collaborate to ensure comprehensive and cohesive policies. Collaboration between the Ministry of Environment, Ministry of Power, and other relevant bodies is crucial to aligning renewable energy goals with broader environmental objectives.

Renewable Energy Incentives: The government provides financial incentives, grants, and subsidies to encourage investment in renewable energy projects. These incentives may include tax breaks, low-interest loans, and support for research and development in sustainable technologies. Regulatory bodies and institutions such as the Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission (NERC) oversee the implementation of feed-in tariffs, ensuring that renewable energy producers receive fair compensation for their contributions to the energy grid.

Capacity Building and Awareness: The government initiates programs to enhance public awareness and build the capacity of stakeholders in the renewable energy sector. This involves training programs, workshops, and campaigns to disseminate information on the benefits of renewable energy. Educational institutions and research centers collaborate with the government to conduct studies, provide expertise, and develop human capital in the field of renewable energy.

Regulatory Frameworks: The government establishes and enforces regulations that guide the integration of renewable energy into the national energy mix. This includes standards for grid connection, power purchase agreements, and environmental impact assessments for renewable projects. Institutions such as the Nigerian Energy Support Programme (NESP) work towards ensuring

that renewable energy projects comply with regulatory standards. They provide guidance and support to project developers to meet environmental and technical requirements.

International Collaboration: The Nigerian government collaborates with international organizations and governments to access funding, technology transfer, and expertise. Such collaborations help align the country's renewable energy efforts with global best practices and climate change mitigation strategies. Institutions involved in renewable energy engage in international networks, fostering collaboration on research, policy development, and the exchange of knowledge and experiences.

Monitoring and Evaluation: Government agencies are tasked with monitoring and evaluating the progress of renewable energy projects and the effectiveness of environmental policies. This involves assessing the impact on emissions reduction, energy access, and overall sustainability. Academic and research institutions contribute by conducting studies and assessments to evaluate the environmental, social, and economic impacts of renewable energy projects. Their findings inform policy adjustments and improvements.

Public-Private Partnerships: The government facilitates partnerships between public and private entities to accelerate renewable energy deployment. This involves creating an enabling environment for private investment through policy frameworks and incentives. Institutions actively engage with private enterprises to bridge gaps in technology, financing, and project implementation. Collaborations aim to optimize resource utilization and enhance the overall impact of renewable energy initiatives.

ASSESSING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF RENEWABLE ENERGY INITIATIVES

Evaluation of Current Renewable Energy Initiatives

Nigeria's renewable energy reserves show great promise, with the government actively pursuing initiatives to harness solar, wind, hydropower, and biomass resources. Ongoing projects and policy support indicate a positive trajectory for the expansion of renewable energy in Nigeria, contributing to both sustainable development and the mitigation of climate change.

Table 1. The Renewable Energy Reserves in Nigeria

Energy sources	Reserves
Small hydropower	3,500 MW
Large hydropower	11,250 MW
Wind	2–4 m/s at 10 m in height (main land)
Solar radiation	3.5–7.0 kWh/m ² /day (4.2 million MWh/day using 0.1% land area)
Animal waste	211 million assorted animal (285.065 million tons/yr of production)
Energy crops and agriculture residue	28.2 million hectares of arable land (30% of total land)
Crop residue	83 million tons/yr
Fuel wood	11 million hectares of forest and wood land
Wave and tidal energy	150,000 TJ/(1,759.6 toe/yr)

Source: Renewable Energy Master Plan (2009).

Table 2. Expected Renewable Energy Growth in Nigeria

Resources	Short (2008)	Medium (2015)	Long (2030)
Large hydropower	1930	5930	48000
Small hydropower	100	734	19000
Solar PV	5	120	500
Solar thermal	1	2	5
Biomass	1	100	800
Wind	1	20	40
All Renewables	2038	6907	68345
All energy resources	16000	30000	192000
% of Renewables	13%	23%	36%

Source: Renewable Energy Master Plan (2009).

Investment Trends

Nigeria has attracted significant investments in renewable energy projects. Both local and international investors are exploring opportunities in the sector, contributing to project funding and implementation. In 2016, Nigeria signed power purchase agreements (PPAs) worth US \$2.5Bn with 14 independent power producers (IPPs) to build a total 1,125 megawatts of installed solar capacity for the national grid.

Solar Nigeria, a £66m UK government initiative, was launched in 2014 to build the market for distributed solar energy in Nigeria. The programme works directly with companies that manufacture, install, and finance solar energy systems in Nigeria. A collaboration between the World Bank, AfDB and the Africa Growing Together Fund led to US \$550 Mn in funding for the NEP. In collaboration with the Chinese government, over US \$5.8 Bn has been invested in adding 3 GW (~25% to current grid capacity) of large hydro supply to the grid, with work to be completed by 2030. This is supplemented by a variety of external investors, including foreign private investors. AfDB is supporting the Nigeria Energy Access Fund (NEAF), a private equity fund backed by Shell, to invest in Renewable Energy opportunities in Nigeria. Pembani Remgro Infrastructure Fund and Israel Capital Ventures are part of a consortium which made a US \$40 Mn equity investment into Nigeria-based SHS company, Lumos. Clean energy funds such as bettervest, and the responsibility Energy Access Fund, have a geographical focus including Nigeria and typically make equity or debt investments of up to US \$3Mn.

Renewable Energy Projects

Nigeria's renewable energy landscape is evolving, with significant projects across solar, wind, and hydropower contributing to the country's energy diversification goals. Ongoing initiatives and policy frameworks reflect a commitment to sustainable development, and as the nation continues to address challenges, the renewable energy sector is poised for further expansion in the coming years.

Table 3. Renewable Energy Projects in Nigeria

Project	Energy Source	Capacity (MW)	Status	Contribution
Azura-Edo Power Plant (Solar and Gas)	Solar and Gas	459	Operational	Significant contribution to the national grid
Benin-Owena River Valley Solar Project	Solar	1.5	Completed	Provides clean energy to the rural community of Ode-Aye in Ondo State.
Katsina Wind Farm	Wind	10	Operational	Contributes to Nigeria's efforts to diversify its energy mix.
Gombe Wind Farm	Wind	30	Under construction	Expected to increase the share of renewable energy in the country.
LafargeHolcim's Calabar Biomass Project	Biomass	16	Under construction	Aiming to utilize biomass for power generation, contributing to cleaner energy.
Egbin Power Plant Solar Project	Solar	50	Under development	Expected to diversify the energy mix and increase solar capacity.
Dangote Cement's Coal to Power Project	Coal (with plans for renewable integration)	1,100	Under development	Includes plans for renewable energy integration to reduce environmental impact.
World Bank's Nigeria Electrification Project (NEP)	Solar Mini- Grids	Various capacities in different mini-grids	Ongoing	Aiming to increase electricity access in rural areas through off-grid renewable solutions.
Solar power plant in Lagos	Solar	1.5	Completed	

Measuring the Impact of Renewable Energy on Climate Change Mitigation

Greenhouse Gas Emission Reduction

The deployment of renewables in the power, heat and transport sectors is one of the main enablers of keeping the rise in average global temperatures below 1.5°C. In the Net Zero Emissions by 2050 scenario, renewables allow electricity generation to be almost completely decarbonised. Meanwhile, renewable transport fuels and renewable heat contribute to significant emissions reductions in transport, buildings and industry. As the world faces the urgent challenge of mitigating climate change, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) has set a goal of achieving a reduction of 50% over pre-industrial levels in global greenhouse gas emissions by 2030. Nigeria, a country that is both rich in natural resources and heavily reliant on fossil fuels, stands at a crossroads in its efforts to contribute to this crucial mission. In line with the country's Nationally Determined Contributions (NDC) submitted to the UNFCCC, Nigeria has committed to cutting emissions by 20% by 2030, comparable to current levels, with the potential to cut emissions by up to 45% with assistance from international sources. Nigeria pledges to transition to a low-carbon economy to support sustainable development and reduce greenhouse gas emissions in line with global goals. The government has identified potential options for reducing emissions, such as increasing the use of carbon sinks or decreasing emissions in energy, oil and gas, agriculture, transportation, and manufacturing sectors.

The Nigerian government has set a target to generate at least 30% of its electricity from renewable sources by 2030. To achieve this, the government has taken several steps to encourage investment in renewable energy, such as creating a feed-in tariff system for renewable energy projects and establishing the Nigerian Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Policy (NREEEP). NREEEP aims to increase the contribution of renewable energy to the country's energy mix by providing incentives for developing renewable energy projects, promoting energy efficiency measures, and enhancing the regulatory framework for renewable energy investments. Despite these policies, however, fossil fuels are still expected to remain a significant part of Nigeria's energy mix for the foreseeable future. This is because the country has significant oil and natural gas reserves, traditionally the country's primary energy source. In addition, the cost of renewable energy is still relatively high in Nigeria, making it less competitive compared to fossil fuels.

Economic Impact of Renewable Energy

- 1. Job Creation:** The development and operation of solar and wind energy projects have led to the creation of jobs in manufacturing, installation, maintenance, and operation. This has a direct impact on employment rates, especially in regions with significant renewable energy projects. The renewable energy sector encourages the development of a skilled local workforce, providing training opportunities and expertise in areas such as solar panel installation, wind turbine maintenance, and hydropower project management.
- 2. Investment Opportunities:** Nigeria has attracted foreign direct investment in its renewable energy sector. International investors see the country's renewable energy potential as an attractive opportunity, contributing to economic growth and infrastructure development. Domestic investors are also increasingly participating in renewable energy projects, stimulated by government incentives and the growing recognition of the economic viability of clean energy ventures.
- 3. Reduction in Energy Costs:** The deployment of renewable energy technologies, particularly solar power, has the potential to reduce energy costs for businesses. This, in turn, enhances the competitiveness of industries and stimulates economic activities. Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in both urban and rural areas benefit from renewable energy solutions, enabling them to access affordable and reliable power, which is crucial for their operations.
- 4. Revenue Generation:** Nigeria's renewable energy sector contributes to revenue generation through potential energy exports. The excess energy generated, especially from large-scale projects, can be sold to neighboring countries, fostering economic cooperation. The growth of renewable energy projects leads to increased tax revenues for the government. Taxes from project developers, manufacturers, and other stakeholders contribute to public finances.
- 5. Energy Security and Economic Stability:** By diversifying its energy mix, Nigeria enhances

energy security, reducing dependence on imported fossil fuels. A stable and diversified energy supply contributes to overall economic stability. Transitioning to renewable energy mitigates economic risks associated with fluctuations in global oil prices, providing a more stable and resilient energy infrastructure.

6. Rural Electrification and Community Development: Rural electrification through off-grid renewable energy projects improves productivity in agricultural activities and small businesses, contributing to economic development in rural areas. Access to renewable energy in rural communities enhances living standards, as it powers healthcare facilities, schools, and other essential services, indirectly contributing to economic growth.

7. Technology Transfer and Innovation: Collaborations with international partners in the renewable energy sector facilitate knowledge and technology transfer. This exchange of expertise fosters innovation and strengthens the technological capabilities of local industries. Investments in renewable energy stimulate research and development activities. This contributes to the growth of a knowledge-based economy and positions Nigeria as a hub for clean energy innovation in the region.

The economic impact of renewable energy in Nigeria extends beyond environmental benefits, playing a crucial role in job creation, investment attraction, cost reduction for businesses, revenue generation, and overall economic development. As the country continues to invest in and adopt renewable energy technologies, these economic benefits are expected to further amplify, contributing to Nigeria's sustainable and resilient economic future.

Social and Environmental Co-Benefits Renewable Energy Projects

Renewable energy projects offer a multifaceted range of social and environmental co-benefits that extend far beyond carbon reduction. Renewable energy sources, such as solar, wind, and hydropower, produce electricity with significantly lower or zero greenhouse gas emissions compared to fossil fuels. This helps mitigate climate change and reduce the environmental impact of energy production. Unlike traditional energy sources, renewable energy projects do not emit pollutants that contribute to air and water pollution. The transition to cleaner energy helps protect ecosystems, improve air quality, and safeguard water resources.

The shift away from fossil fuels results in decreased air pollution, leading to improved respiratory health. Communities surrounding renewable energy projects experience fewer respiratory illnesses, particularly among vulnerable populations such as children and the elderly. Renewable energy projects reduce the risk of environmental hazards associated with the extraction, transportation, and combustion of fossil fuels. This, in turn, minimizes public health risks related to accidents, spills, and pollution.

The installation, operation, and maintenance of renewable energy projects create job opportunities at the local level. This includes positions in manufacturing, installation, and ongoing maintenance, fostering economic development in communities. The growth of renewable energy sectors stimulates the economy by attracting investments, fostering innovation, and Off-grid renewable energy projects, such as solar mini-grids, contribute to rural electrification. This improves access to electricity in remote areas, enhancing economic opportunities, education, and healthcare. Renewable energy projects, particularly those based on solar power, provide affordable and decentralized energy solutions. This benefits low-income communities by reducing energy costs and improving living conditions.

Unlike large-scale conventional energy projects that may disrupt ecosystems, many renewable energy installations have a smaller footprint. This minimizes habitat disruption and helps protect biodiversity. Mitigating climate change through the use of renewable energy supports ecosystems and biodiversity by reducing the frequency and intensity of extreme weather events, preserving habitats critical for various species.

Community-based renewable energy projects, such as wind or solar cooperatives, empower local communities by allowing them to own and manage energy installations. This creates a sense of ownership and enhances community resilience. Participation in renewable energy projects fosters social cohesion within communities. Collaborative decision-making and shared benefits contribute to stronger social bonds and increased community well-being.

Unlike conventional power plants, which often require large amounts of water for cooling, many renewable energy technologies, such as solar and wind, have minimal water usage. This helps conserve water resources, especially in arid regions. Hydropower projects can be designed with a focus on minimizing negative impacts on aquatic ecosystems. Considerations such as fish-friendly turbines and downstream flow maintenance contribute to environmental conservation.

Renewable energy projects provide educational opportunities for communities, schools, and individuals. Learning about clean energy technologies fosters awareness, environmental stewardship, and a skilled workforce for the future. Visible renewable energy installations serve as educational tools and raise awareness about the feasibility and benefits of transitioning to clean energy, inspiring further environmental consciousness.

Diversifying the energy mix with renewables enhances energy security by reducing dependence on imported fossil fuels. This resilience to energy shocks contributes to economic stability and national security. Distributed renewable energy sources, such as rooftop solar panels, contribute to a more resilient energy infrastructure by reducing the vulnerability associated with centralized power generation and distribution. The deployment of renewable energy projects stimulates research and development in clean energy technologies. Innovation in energy storage, grid integration, and efficiency improvements contributes to environmental sustainability and economic growth. Collaborations and partnerships in renewable energy projects facilitate the transfer of clean energy technologies, promoting global knowledge sharing and accelerating the adoption of sustainable practices.

As Nigeria and other countries embrace these projects, they contribute to a more sustainable, equitable, and resilient future. The realization of these co-benefits underscores the holistic impact of transitioning to clean energy solutions in the pursuit of global sustainability goals.

Progress in Achieving Climate Change Mitigation Goals Through Renewable Energy Adoption

Nigeria has demonstrated commendable progress in adopting renewable energy as part of its strategy to mitigate climate change. The concerted efforts of the government, private sector, and international partners contribute to building a more sustainable and resilient energy future for the nation. Here are key aspects indicating the progress in achieving climate change mitigation goals through renewable energy adoption in Nigeria:

- 1. Increasing Renewable Energy Capacity:** Nigeria has witnessed a substantial increase in renewable energy capacity, particularly in solar and wind power. The deployment of utility-scale solar projects and the exploration of wind energy potential contribute to diversifying the energy mix. Notable solar projects, including grid-connected solar farms and off-grid solar installations, have been implemented across the country, contributing to increased renewable energy capacity.
- 2. Policy Frameworks and Incentives:** The Nigerian government has developed and implemented policy frameworks to support renewable energy development. The National Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Policy (NREEEP) and the Renewable Energy Master Plan (REMP) provide strategic guidelines for renewable energy deployment. Incentives such as tax breaks, grants, and favorable tariffs for renewable energy projects have been introduced to attract investments and stimulate growth in the sector.
- 3. Off-Grid and Rural Electrification:** Off-grid renewable energy solutions, particularly solar mini-grids, play a crucial role in providing electricity to rural and underserved communities. These initiatives contribute to rural electrification and improve energy access in areas with limited or no connection to the national grid. The Rural Electrification Agency (REA) has been actively involved in promoting off-grid renewable energy projects to address energy poverty in remote areas.
- 4. Renewable Energy Investments:** Increased investments from both domestic and international sources have been directed toward renewable energy projects in Nigeria. Public-private partnerships and foreign direct investments support the development of utility-scale renewable energy infrastructure. The private sector's involvement in renewable energy projects, including independent power producers (IPPs), reflects growing confidence in the economic viability of clean energy solutions.

5. Diversification of Energy Mix: The Nigerian government has prioritized the diversification of the energy mix to reduce dependence on fossil fuels. This diversification includes a greater focus on renewable sources such as solar, wind, biomass, and hydropower. Efforts to integrate renewable energy into the national grid contribute to a more balanced and sustainable energy portfolio.

6. Climate Finance and International Cooperation: Nigeria has engaged in international collaborations and climate finance mechanisms to support renewable energy projects. Participation in climate funds and partnerships with international organizations facilitates the mobilization of resources for sustainable energy initiatives. The country's commitment to international climate agreements, such as the Paris Agreement, underscores its dedication to addressing climate change through renewable energy adoption.

7. Awareness and Capacity Building: Increasing awareness about the benefits of renewable energy adoption has been a focus of government and non-governmental initiatives. Public awareness campaigns and capacity-building programs contribute to changing perceptions and fostering a culture of sustainable energy use. Educational institutions and research centers are actively involved in promoting research and development in renewable energy technologies.

8. Integration of Technology and Innovation: Ongoing efforts in research, development, and innovation contribute to the integration of advanced technologies in renewable energy projects. Innovations in energy storage, grid management, and efficiency improvements enhance the overall performance of renewable energy systems. Collaborations with global research institutions and technology transfer initiatives contribute to the modernization of the renewable energy sector.

9. Government Commitment and Legislation: The commitment of the Nigerian government to achieving climate change mitigation goals is reflected in legislative measures and institutional support. The introduction of the Climate Change Act and other regulatory frameworks emphasizes the importance of addressing climate challenges. Government-led initiatives, such as the Nigeria Electrification Project (NEP), aim to accelerate the deployment of renewable energy solutions across the country.

Carbon Footprint Reduction and Environmental Sustainability

The role of renewable energies in the sustainable energy governance and environmental policies for the mitigation of climate change in Nigeria is intimately tied to the imperative of reducing carbon footprints and fostering environmental sustainability. The adoption of renewable energies, such as solar, wind, and hydropower, facilitates a shift away from fossil fuels, which are major contributors to carbon emissions. This transition is foundational for reducing the carbon footprint of energy generation in Nigeria. Renewable energy sources produce electricity with significantly lower greenhouse gas emissions compared to conventional fossil fuels. The deployment of solar panels, wind turbines, and other clean technologies contributes directly to mitigating climate change by curbing emissions. Beyond the energy source itself, renewable energy systems often encourage energy efficiency. For instance, the installation of energy-efficient appliances alongside solar panels enhances overall sustainability by reducing energy demand. Renewable energy technologies, particularly solar, offer opportunities for decentralized energy production. This decentralization not only enhances energy resilience but also minimizes transmission losses, contributing to a more sustainable and efficient energy infrastructure. The integration of renewable energies aligns with green building practices. In Nigeria, where rapid urbanization is occurring, sustainable infrastructure development, including energy-efficient buildings and smart grids powered by renewables, can significantly reduce carbon footprints. The use of renewable energies for rural electrification addresses energy poverty while promoting environmental sustainability. By providing clean energy alternatives to off-grid communities, the reliance on traditional, carbon-intensive energy sources, like kerosene lamps, is diminished.

Investing in renewable energy projects stimulates economic diversification. The growth of the renewable sector not only reduces carbon emissions but also creates job opportunities, fostering a sustainable and inclusive economy. Renewable energy initiatives should be integrated into comprehensive environmental policies. This involves setting clear targets for carbon reduction, enforcing emissions standards, and promoting sustainable practices across industries. Continuous research and innovation in renewable energy technologies are essential for enhancing efficiency and

reducing costs. Government support for research institutions and private sector collaboration can drive advancements in clean energy solutions. Environmental sustainability is reinforced through public awareness and education. Educational programs highlighting the benefits of renewable energies and the environmental consequences of carbon-intensive practices contribute to a culture of sustainability. Implementing robust monitoring and reporting mechanisms ensures that carbon footprint reduction goals are met. Regular assessments of environmental impacts and the effectiveness of renewable energy projects inform policy adjustments for continual improvement.

CHALLENGES, RECOMMENDATIONS, AND CONCLUSION

Identifying Challenges and Obstacles

1. Regulatory Policies: Regulatory policies are essential in the successful implementation of renewable energy in a country. Inconsistent or unclear policies and regulations can create uncertainty for investors and project developers. A stable and supportive policy environment is crucial for attracting investment in the renewable energy sector. Nigeria does not have a good regulatory policy on renewable energy. However, in 2005, the Energy commission of Nigeria (ECN) came up with a National Renewable Energy Master Plan (REMP), in light of the goals of National Energy Policy, National Policy on Integrated Rural Development, the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and the National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS). These programs do not capitalize on the opportunities presented in the remote, rural, mountainous and riverine regions. Thus, the renewable energy master plan provides a good opportunity for the nation's renewable energy harness, but is not a national policy on renewable energy.

2. Finance and Market Size: Huge capital is the main obstacle for remote, rural, mountainous and riverine renewable energy projects. Majority of renewable energy projects have very high initial cost, but long life span, with little or no running cost when compared to other conventional energy sources like diesel type. The upfront costs associated with installing renewable energy systems, such as solar panels or wind turbines, can be relatively high. This poses a financial barrier, especially for individuals or businesses with limited capital. Unfortunately, many consumers especially in the remote rural, mountainous and riverine regions with low income prefer to keep the initial cost low rather than minimize the operating cost which would run over a long period of time [23]. Therefore a call for sustainable and realistic renewable energy market opportunity projects is needed by private sector as against governmental and foreign agencies projects. Limited access to financing or loans for renewable energy projects can also hinder adoption. Financial institutions may be unfamiliar with the risks associated with renewable projects, making them hesitant to provide loans.

3. Technological Knowhow: Average Nigerians lack the technical skills to contain modern trends of renewable energy technology. This is a big challenge especially in the areas of inadequate and inaccurate resource data, low product quality, little or no research and development activity, and lack of human and manufacturing abilities. The worst scenario is the lack of knowledge among users and installers in the event of distinguishing between good and bad equipment and make the right choice [24]. Nigerian University Commission (NUC) should be of help in this regard to include renewable energy education in the curriculum of Nigerian schools, and government should create enabling platform and environment for the encouragement of indigenous renewable energy technology.

4. Institutional Problem: Nigeria lacks good institutes to lead renewable energy technology, hence the direction and coordination of renewable energy activities in the country is a fiasco. The present research centres lack the ability to commercialize their developed products. On the other hand, there are opportunities for the present renewable energy master plan to establish national renewable energy agency that should encourage efficiency in the provision and use of the various types of energy. This would be with respect to improve the quality of training and management of energy, and also enlighten or create awareness of energy related matters to champion local institutional reforms in order to help meet policy targets to reduce environmental risk.

5. Socio Cultural Habits: Generally, renewable energy technologies are sensed to create discomfort or sacrifice rather than as providing relevant energy services with reduced cost [23]. The cultural and religious beliefs of the people have a role to play in terms of the understanding and

concern of the people in the vicinity where renewable energy technology is enacted. The opportunities that renewable energy offers need to be intimated to the people in the small remote, mountainous and riverine area, as this would enhance the optimal operation of renewable technology in these areas.

6. Infrastructure Limitations: Weak or inadequate grid infrastructure can limit the capacity to absorb electricity generated from renewable sources. Upgrading and expanding the grid are essential for successful integration of renewable energy.

7. Public Awareness and Perception: Lack of awareness about the benefits of renewable energy and misconceptions about its reliability may lead to resistance or reluctance among consumers. Public awareness campaigns are crucial to promote the advantages of renewable energy. Awareness of the opportunities offered by renewable energies and their technologies is low among public and private sectors. This lack of information and awareness creates a market gap that results in higher risk perception for potential renewable energy projects. The general perception is that renewable energy technologies are not yet mature technologies, hence are only suited for niche markets and as such will require heavy subsidy to make it work. There is therefore a need for dissemination of information on renewable energy resource availability, benefits and opportunity to the general public in order to raise public awareness and generate activities in the area. Such process is paramount to building public confidence and acceptance of renewable energy technology. Providing information to selected stakeholder groups like the investors can help mobilize financial resources needed to promote renewable energy technology projects. The draft Renewable Energy Master Plan proposes the set-up of a National Renewable Energy Development Agency (NREDA), which can assist in increasing public awareness and providing information and assistance to interested stakeholders. This is to be done together with non-governmental organizations (NGOs)

8. Land Use and Space Requirements: Some renewable energy projects, such as large-scale solar farms or wind installations, may face conflicts related to land use. Balancing the need for renewable energy development with other land uses is essential.

9. Availability of Fossil Fuels: Subsidies on conventional energy sources, such as fossil fuels, can create an uneven playing field for renewable energy. Governments may need to reconsider or phase out subsidies to level the economic playing field.

10. Market Dynamics: The concentration of the energy market in the hands of a few players may limit competition and hinder the entry of renewable energy projects. Encouraging a more competitive market can promote renewable energy adoption.

11. Political and Economic Stability: Political instability and uncertainties can deter investors from committing to long-term renewable energy projects. A stable political and economic environment is crucial for attracting investment.

12. Supply Chain Disruptions: Reliance on imported components for renewable energy systems can lead to supply chain disruptions. Encouraging local manufacturing and reducing dependence on imports can mitigate this risk.

13. Grid Integration Issues: The intermittency of renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind, can pose challenges for grid integration. Ensuring a reliable and stable power supply from renewable sources requires effective energy storage solutions and grid management.

Recommendations for Enhancing Renewable Energy Adoption

1. Policy Continuity and Stability: Ensure continuity and stability in renewable energy policies to provide a predictable and supportive environment for investors. Long-term policy commitments reduce uncertainties and attract sustained investments in the sector.

2. Capacity Building and Research: Invest in capacity building programs for professionals in the renewable energy sector. This includes training for technicians, engineers, and policymakers to enhance skills and knowledge related to renewable energy technologies. Encourage research and development activities in collaboration with academic institutions to drive innovation in renewable energy solutions and address specific challenges faced in the Nigerian context.

3. Financial Mechanisms and Incentives: Establish and enhance financial mechanisms, such as feed-in tariffs, tax credits, and subsidies, to make renewable energy projects financially viable and attractive to investors. Explore public-private partnerships and innovative financing models to mobilize both domestic and international capital for large-scale renewable energy projects.

4. Grid Integration and Infrastructure Development: Improve the integration of renewable energy into the national grid through the development of smart grids and grid management technologies. This ensures a reliable and stable electricity supply from renewable sources. Invest in grid infrastructure upgrades to accommodate the increased penetration of intermittent renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind.

5. Off-Grid Solutions for Rural Electrification: Prioritize and scale up off-grid renewable energy solutions, particularly in rural and remote areas with limited access to the national grid. This will contribute to rural electrification and improve energy access for underserved communities. Support decentralized renewable energy projects, including solar mini-grids and standalone systems, to address localized energy needs.

6. Community Engagement and Awareness: Foster community engagement and awareness programs to educate the public about the benefits of renewable energy. This includes campaigns highlighting the economic, social, and environmental advantages of adopting clean energy solutions. Involve local communities in decision-making processes related to renewable energy projects to ensure their needs and concerns are considered.

7. Regulatory Framework and Standards: Strengthen and enforce regulatory frameworks related to renewable energy development. This includes setting clear standards for project approvals, environmental impact assessments, and safety protocols. Streamline and simplify regulatory processes to facilitate the timely implementation of renewable energy projects.

8. International Collaboration and Climate Finance: Collaborate with international organizations, development partners, and climate finance institutions to access funding for renewable energy projects. Participation in global initiatives enhances financial and technical support for sustainable energy development. Align national renewable energy goals with international climate change agreements and commitments to leverage support and cooperation.

9. Innovation and Technology Transfer: Encourage technology transfer and collaboration with international research institutions and technology providers. This facilitates the adoption of advanced and cost-effective renewable energy technologies in Nigeria. Create platforms for knowledge exchange and collaboration between local innovators, researchers, and global experts in the renewable energy sector.

10. Inclusive Policies for Social Impact: Implement inclusive policies that ensure the social impact of renewable energy projects benefits all segments of the population. This includes policies promoting job creation, skills development, and community empowerment in the renewable energy sector. Prioritize projects that address energy poverty, particularly in marginalized and vulnerable communities, to enhance social equity.

11. Monitoring and Evaluation: Establish a robust monitoring and evaluation framework to assess the performance and impact of renewable energy projects. Regular evaluations help identify challenges, measure progress, and inform future policy decisions. Utilize data-driven insights to continuously improve the effectiveness of renewable energy initiatives and address emerging issues.

12. Public-Private Collaboration: Foster collaboration between the public and private sectors to leverage expertise, resources, and innovation. Public-private partnerships can accelerate the deployment of renewable energy projects and enhance overall sector efficiency. Create platforms for dialogue and cooperation between government agencies, private companies, and civil society to collectively address challenges and capitalize on opportunities in the renewable energy sector.

Implementing these recommendations requires a coordinated and multi-stakeholder approach. By addressing the key areas outlined above, Nigeria can enhance the adoption of renewable energy, contribute to sustainable development, and achieve its climate change mitigation goals.

Strengthening Climate Change Mitigation Strategies

Nigeria needs to take significant steps towards mitigating the impacts of climate change. Here are some steps that Nigeria can take:

- **Invest in Renewable Energy:** Nigeria needs to invest heavily in renewable energy sources such as solar, wind, and hydroelectric power. This will reduce the reliance on fossil fuels for energy generation and lead to a reduction in greenhouse gas emissions.
- **Improve Energy Efficiency:** Nigeria must improve energy efficiency by encouraging energy-efficient appliances and buildings. This will reduce energy demand and hence reduce greenhouse gas emissions.
- **Encourage Sustainable Transportation:** Nigeria needs to encourage the use of sustainable transportation, such as electric vehicles and mass transit systems. This will reduce emissions from the transport sector.
- **Adopt Sustainable Agricultural Practices:** Nigeria needs to adopt sustainable agricultural practices that reduce emissions from the agriculture sector. This includes practices such as conservation agriculture and agroforestry.
- **Reduce Deforestation:** Nigeria must reduce deforestation by implementing policies promoting sustainable land use and forest management. This will reduce emissions from the land-use sector.
- **Encourage Waste Management:** Nigeria needs to encourage waste management practices that reduce emissions from the waste sector. This includes waste reduction, reuse, and recycling.
- **Collaborate with the International Community:** Nigeria needs to collaborate with the international community to access financial, technological, and capacity-building support. This will help Nigeria implement climate change mitigation measures more effectively.

Summary of Key Findings

1. Energy Transition Imperative:

Nigeria faces a critical need to transition from its heavy reliance on fossil fuels to renewable energy sources to mitigate the adverse effects of climate change. The current energy mix, dominated by oil and gas, is not sustainable in the long term and exacerbates environmental challenges, including greenhouse gas emissions.

2. Abundant Renewable Energy Resources:

Nigeria possesses abundant renewable energy resources, including solar, wind, hydro, and biomass, which have the potential to meet its energy needs sustainably. Solar energy, in particular, is a promising source given the country's high solar irradiance levels.

3. Policy Framework and Regulation:

Effective governance and supportive environmental policies are crucial to harnessing renewable energy's potential. The Nigerian government has taken initial steps by developing policies, such as the Renewable Energy Master Plan (The Renewable Energy Master Plan (REMP) seeks to increase the supply of renewable electricity from 13% of total electricity generation in 2015 to 23% in 2025 and 36% by 2030. Renewable electricity would then account for 10% of Nigerian total energy consumption by 2025) and the National Energy Policy, to promote renewable energy adoption.

4. Barriers to Adoption:

Despite the potential, there are several barriers to the widespread adoption of renewable energy in Nigeria, including financial constraints, inadequate infrastructure, and a lack of public awareness. Additionally, regulatory and administrative challenges have hindered the development of the renewable energy sector.

5. Economic Benefits:

The transition to renewable energy can bring economic benefits, including job creation, reduced energy costs, and increased energy access, especially in rural areas. Investments in renewable energy projects can attract foreign direct investment and stimulate economic growth.

6. Mitigation of Climate Change:

The adoption of renewable energies in Nigeria is crucial for mitigating climate change as it reduces greenhouse gas emissions, contributing to global efforts to combat climate change. Sustainable energy practices can help Nigeria meet its climate commitments under international agreements like the Paris Agreement.

7. International Collaboration:

Collaborative efforts with international organizations and donor agencies can facilitate technology transfer, capacity building, and financial support for renewable energy projects in Nigeria. Partnerships can also assist in overcoming financial barriers to renewable energy development.

8. Public Awareness and Education:

Raising public awareness and providing education on the benefits of renewable energy is essential to promote its adoption in Nigeria. Information campaigns and training programs can help dispel myths and misconceptions about renewable energy technologies.

9. Rural Electrification:

Renewable energies can play a pivotal role in rural electrification efforts, bringing power to underserved areas and improving the quality of life for rural communities. Off-grid and decentralized renewable energy solutions can be particularly beneficial in this regard.

10. Long-Term Sustainability:

The transition to renewable energies in Nigeria is a long-term endeavor that requires a sustained commitment from the government, private sector, and civil society. A comprehensive, integrated approach to energy governance and environmental policy is necessary to ensure the sustainability of this transition.

Conclusion

Nigeria, facing the dual challenge of meeting escalating energy demands and mitigating climate change impacts, stands at a critical juncture in its energy transition. The research reveals a promising landscape for renewable energy adoption, driven by abundant resources and governmental initiatives. The country's commitment to policy formulation, technological exploration, and environmental alignment showcases strides toward sustainable energy governance. However, challenges persist, ranging from regulatory inconsistencies to financial barriers and technological knowhow limitations. Addressing these challenges requires sustained policy continuity, capacity building, and innovative financial mechanisms. The findings underscore the imperative for Nigeria to embrace a comprehensive and stable renewable energy policy, fostering a conducive environment for investment and technological advancements. In conclusion, the research underscores that the symbiotic relationship between renewable energies, governance structures, and environmental policies is integral to Nigeria's sustainable development. As the nation charts its course toward a renewable energy future, strategic policy interventions, technological innovations, and international collaborations will play pivotal roles in shaping a sustainable and resilient energy landscape.

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